

STUDIES IN THE *iso*QUINOLINE SERIES. PART I

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Experiments are described in which selenium has been used in the dehydrogenation of some 1-aryl-3:4-dihydroisoquinolines.

The Bischler-Napieralski synthesis (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1903) is a valuable method for the preparation of a large number of *iso*quinoline compounds and has found extensive use in the field of alkaloids. It consists in the treatment of the acyl derivatives (both aliphatic and aromatic) of β -phenylethylamine with powerful dehydrating agents such as phosphorus pentoxide, phosphorus oxychloride or polyphosphoric acid in boiling toluene, xylene or tetraline, whereby a 3:4-dihydroisoquinoline is produced (Späth, Berger and Kuntara, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 134; Whaley and Hartung, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 650; Snyder and Werber, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2962 *et seq.*).

The dihydroisoquinoline formed can be converted into true *iso*quinoline compound either by oxidation or by one of the dehydrogenation methods. Thus, Pictet and Kay (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 1973) prepared 1-phenyl- and 1-benzyl-*iso*quinolines by the oxidation of the corresponding 3:4-dihydro compound with potassium permanganate in acid solution, while Späth and his collaborators (*loc. cit.*) elaborated the method of catalytic dehydrogenation with palladium for the preparation of a large number of *iso*quinoline compounds. This latter method has been found to be very useful, irrespective of the nature of the side-chain at position *one* and the yields obtained are very high.

Besides the catalytic method of dehydrogenation, the other methods available are the dehydrogenation with sulphur at a low temperature or with the less destructive selenium at higher temperatures. 1-Phenyl-3:4-dihydro- and 1-methyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinolines, which were prepared in yields of 72% and 58% respectively according to the modified procedure of Whaley and Hartung (*loc. cit.*), were subjected to selenium dehydrogenation in accordance with the usual procedure. The temperatures of reaction used were 300°-320° for the 1-phenyl- and 240°-260° for the corresponding 1-methyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline and a reaction time of about 40 to 50 hours was employed. It was found that the dehydrogenation of these compounds into the true *iso*quinolines took place smoothly and the pure final compounds were obtained in yields of 55%. The yields are considerably lower than those in the case of catalytic dehydrogenations and the method is of limited use. Perhaps the lower yields could be explained on the basis that in the beginning the reaction is very vigorous and some of the material is lost by being carried over with the escaping hydrogen selenide.

No other 1-aryl-3:4-dihydroisoquinolines were subjected to this method of dehydrogenation, as it is well known in the field of steroids that the presence of longer side-chains leads to complications.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Preparation of 1-Phenyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline.—The procedure of Whaley and Hartung (*loc. cit.*) was used. *N*-Benzoyl- β -phenylethylamine (9 g.) was heated with phosphorus pentoxide (30 g.) and POCl_3 (30 g.) in xylene (75 c.c.) for 4 hours on a sand-bath. The mixture was poured on ice and the xylene layer separated. The water layer was basified with a solution of caustic soda and 1-phenyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline extracted with benzene. The oil (9.1 g.) obtained was fractionally distilled. The portion, b.p. $185^\circ/10$ mm. (lit., $190^\circ\text{--}200^\circ/12$ mm.) was collected, yield, 6 g. (72%).

Preparation of 1-Methyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline.—*N*-Acetyl- β -phenylethylamine (10 g.) was heated with phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (20 g.) in xylene (150 c.c.) for 2 hours. The crude oil (6.7 g.) isolated as above was fractionally distilled and collected at $128^\circ/10$ mm. (lit., $130^\circ/10$ mm.), yield 5 g. (58%).

Selenium Dehydrogenations: Preparation of 1-Phenylisoquinoline.—1-Phenyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (6 g.) was heated with powdered selenium (16 g.) in a long necked pyrex flask, fitted with a long air condenser and heated in a metal bath, maintained at $300^\circ\text{--}320^\circ$. A brisk reaction took place for the first few hours with a vigorous evolution of hydrogen selenide gas. After heating for a total period of 42 hours, the flask was cooled. The compound was extracted with benzene, which was boiled with animal charcoal several times, to get rid of the last traces of selenium and then filtered. The benzene was then distilled off leaving an amorphous solid, m.p. $91\text{--}92^\circ$ (lit., 93°) yield 3.2 g. (55%). The picrate (prepared from ethyl alcohol) has a m.p. $165\text{--}66^\circ$ (lit., m. p. $165\text{--}66^\circ$).

Preparation of 1-Methylisoquinoline.—1-Methyl-3:4-dihydroisoquinoline (5 g.) was similarly heated with powdered selenium (11 g.) in a metal bath at $240^\circ\text{--}260^\circ$. After heating for a total period of 48 hours, the compound was isolated as above. The crude oil was then fractionated. 1-Methylisoquinoline was collected at $125^\circ/10$ mm. (lit., $124^\circ\text{--}126^\circ/10$ mm.), yield 2.7 g. (55%). The picrate (prepared from methyl alcohol) has a m.p. $224\text{--}25^\circ$ (decomp.) (lit., m.p. $225\text{--}26^\circ$).